

Dispensing and counseling practices of topical antibiotics among community pharmacists in Saudi Arabia: a cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Background: Improper use of topical antibiotics contributes significantly to antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

Objective: This study assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of community pharmacists in Saudi Arabia regarding the dispensing of topical antibiotics.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted in January 2024 among 233 community pharmacists using descriptive and logistic regression analyses.

Results: Although 82% of participants recognized that inappropriate dispensing contributes to AMR, 69.1% incorrectly believed dispensing without a prescription is legal. Significant knowledge gaps were identified, with 90% unable to identify correct indications for several common formulations. Counseling barriers included time constraints (45%) and negative patient perceptions (53.6%).

Conclusions: Despite awareness of AMR risks, substantial gaps in regulatory knowledge and clinical practice persist among community pharmacists. Targeted educational interventions and stricter enforcement of prescription-only regulations are essential to promote responsible use and safeguard public health.

Keywords

Topical antibiotics, Community pharmacists, Antibiotic resistance, Counseling practices, Saudi Arabia

Introduction

Topical antibiotics are crucial in treating various skin infections, as they are specifically designed to be applied directly to the affected area. These antibiotics work by targeting and killing bacteria on the skin's surface or inhibiting their growth (Bandyopadhyay 2021). Antibiotic resistance occurs when bacteria develop the ability to survive and multiply in the presence of antibiotics, rendering

these medications less effective or completely ineffective. This phenomenon poses a significant global health challenge, as it limits treatment options and increases the risk of infections becoming more severe and difficult to control (Prestinaci et al. 2015).

The development of antibiotic resistance is a significant concern in topical antibiotics (Gold and Moellering 1996). This is particularly relevant in the treatment of bacterial

skin infections, where topical antibiotics are common (Williamson et al. 2017). However, the link between topical antibiotic formulations and the development of resistance is not well-established (Jones 1999). The emergence of resistance to topical antibiotics is a growing concern in dermatology, particularly in treating methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) infections (Elston 2009). This resistance can result from the topical application of antibiotics, leading to the development of resistant strains (Epstein 1967). Nong et al. (2023) investigated the effect of topical antibiotic use in co-selecting for MRSA through *in vitro* and *ex vivo* models and found that *fusC* gene carriage confers resistance to fusidic acid, and *mupA* gene carriage confers high-level resistance to mupirocin. However, the use of topical antimicrobial wash products has not been definitively linked to the development of resistance (Jones, 1999). Despite this, the potential for microbial resistance to topical antimicrobial mixtures has been assessed, with some success in reducing the likelihood of resistance (Holder and Boyce 1999). Despite this, the potential for antibiotic resistance remains a key consideration when using these agents, as it can negatively impact patient outcomes and well-being (Williamson et al. 2017). Promoting judicious and responsible use of topical antibiotics is crucial to combat antibiotic resistance, ensuring they are used only when necessary and under professional medical guidance.

The relationship between community pharmacists' knowledge, attitude, and practice and dispensing systemic antibiotics has been investigated. In a cross-sectional survey conducted between January and February 2016, involving 189 community pharmacists, more than two-thirds (70.5%) were unaware that dispensing antibiotics without a prescription is illegal. Lack of willingness to consult a physician for a non-serious infection (69.9%) and inability to afford a consultation (65.3%) were the most common reasons for using antibiotics without a prescription. A statistically significant association was found between the number of antibiotics dispensed and educating patients about the importance of adherence and completing the entire course of antibiotics ($p = 0.007$), indicating that patient education was associated with fewer antibiotics dispensed without a prescription (Hadi et al. 2016).

In another cross-sectional study conducted in community pharmacies within Kedah State, Malaysia, 53.4% of community pharmacists perceived that topical antibacterial is unnecessary for every topical bacterial infection. Fusidic acid was the most frequently dispensed topical antibacterial drug, while the superficial wound was reported to be the most commonly encountered topical bacterial infection. 12.6% of participants experienced cases of antibacterial resistance, but none reported them. The drug that had resistance issues was neomycin (Amirthalingam et al. 2016). However, that study did not specify how pharmacists detect antibacterial resistance in community pharmacies. Also, they did not describe how resistance cases would be reported, nor whether reporting resistance is required by law in that country.

In 2018, the Ministry of Health (MOH) in Saudi Arabia announced new enforcement of the Executive Regulations

of the Health Practice Law, which prohibit dispensing antibiotics without a prescription and regulate antibiotic use (MOH 2018). The MOH warned those selling antibiotics without a prescription that they could be fined up to SAR 100,000. These regulations apply to both systemic and topical antibiotics and are unified across the country.

To date, comprehensive and focused studies have not been conducted to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices that community pharmacists in Saudi Arabia possess when dispensing topical antibiotics. This information is crucial for identifying potential gaps in their understanding and determining how well they adhere to established clinical practice guidelines for treating skin and soft tissue infections (Stevens et al. 2014) and national protocols (MOH 2026). Furthermore, it could provide insights into the factors influencing their decision to dispense topical antibiotics, whether with or without a prescription, including their training and experience, as well as external pressures or incentives. By better understanding these issues, healthcare providers and policymakers could implement targeted interventions to improve the quality and safety of pharmacy services and support the responsible use of antibiotics in the community. Thus, our study aimed to assess community pharmacists' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding the dispensing of topical antibiotics.

Materials and methods

Study design, setting, and sample selection

This was a cross-sectional study of community pharmacists surveyed in January 2024. Our inclusion criteria were pharmacists working in community pharmacies in Saudi Arabia who consented to participate in the survey.

Survey instruments

The survey was adapted from a previous study that assessed the dispensing and counseling practices for topical corticosteroids and modified for our study's objectives (Kang et al. 2020). During the development of the survey, a content and face validity process was conducted to ensure that the survey was valid and relevant to the subject matter. This process involved soliciting feedback from five community pharmacists with relevant experience in the field. The survey was carefully reviewed and evaluated, and the community pharmacists provided comments and suggestions for improvement.

Based on their feedback, the survey was modified to ensure that it accurately captured relevant information and was easy for the study population to understand. The final version of the survey was then distributed to the study population, ensuring that it accurately reflected the subject matter and met the needs of the research project (See Suppl. material 1: appendix S1 for a copy of the final version of the survey).

Study procedures

The survey was created using Google Forms (Google LLC, Menlo Park, California, United States). The online version of the survey was distributed using social media platforms (Facebook, WhatsApp, X, etc.). The study investigators also visited some community pharmacies in person and provided them with a QR code to complete the survey. Finally, the administration of the large chain pharmacies in Saudi Arabia was contacted and provided with the survey link to distribute to their employees.

Sample size calculations

Using the online Raosoft® sample size calculator (Raosoft Inc., Seattle, WA, USA) (Raosoft Inc. 2004), based on an estimated population of 20,900 community pharmacists in Saudi Arabia according to the 2021 Ministry of Health (MOH) data (SDAIA 2025) with a confidence interval (CI) of 95%, a margin of error of 5%, and a response rate of 50%, a minimum sample size of 378 participants would be needed for this study. Therefore, the required sample size is rounded up to 400 participants.

Statistical analysis

The data were summarized using descriptive statistics in Jamovi (2023) version 2.3. Depending on the variable type, medians with interquartile ranges were used for continuous variables, and counts with percentages were used for categorical variables. A Z-test was used to compare the categories of pharmacists' knowledge of the appropriate indications for topical antibiotic dispensing. We performed

an exploratory univariable logistic regression analysis to assess associations between demographics and attitudes toward antibiotic dispensing, and we reported the results as odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs).

Results

Demographics

A total of 4000 community pharmacists were randomly invited to participate in the study, and 233 completed the survey, representing a response rate of 5.8%. Among those responses, 32 were female (13.7%). The median age of the participants is 31 years (IQR 23–55). Most of the surveyed community pharmacists are non-Saudi (75.1%) and hold a Bachelor's degree in Pharmacy (73.8%). The sample was reasonably distributed across the regions of Saudi Arabia, with the Eastern Province recording the highest response (29.6%), followed by the Western Province (22.7%), the Northern Province (19.3%), the Southern Province (15%), and the Central Province (13.3%). Most community pharmacists had between 5 and 9 years of experience (29.2%) and 10 to 14 years (28.8%). The demographics are summarized in Table 1.

Dispensing knowledge, attitude, and practices

Practices

Most community pharmacists reported dispensing about 25 or fewer topical antibiotics per day (85.4%), and only 1.7% reported dispensing more than 50. The most commonly

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of the Surveyed Participants (N = 233).

Characteristic	Region of Practice				
	Central Province, n (%)	Northern Province, n (%)	Southern Province, n (%)	Western Province, n (%)	Eastern Province, n (%)
Gender					
Male	26 (11)	42 (18)	30 (12.8)	45 (19.3)	58 (24.8)
Female	5 (2.1)	3 (1.2)	5 (2.1)	8 (3.4)	11 (4.7)
Nationality					
Saudi	5 (2.1)	5 (2.1)	11 (4.7)	15 (6.4)	22 (9.4)
Non-Saudi	26 (11.1)	40 (17.1)	24 (10.3)	38 (16.3)	47 (20.1)
Level of Education					
Bachelor of pharmacy	24 (10.3)	38 (16.3)	26 (11.1)	40 (17.1)	44 (18.8)
Doctor of pharmacy	4 (1.7)	7 (3)	8 (3.4)	11 (4.7)	21 (9)
PGY1	2 (0.8)	0	1 (0.4)	2 (0.8)	3 (1.2)
PGY2	1 (0.4)				1 (0.4)
Years of Experience					
0 – <2 years	1 (0.4)	3 (1.2)	4 (1.7)	9 (3.8)	14 (6)
2–4 years	6 (2.5)	6 (2.5)	7 (3)	7 (3)	6 (2.5)
5–9 years	8 (3.4)	14 (6)	15 (6.4)	14 (6)	17 (7.2)
10–14 years	13 (5.5)	11 (4.7)	9 (3.8)	13 (5.5)	21 (9)
15–19 years	2 (0.8)	8 (3.4)	0	7 (3)	8 (3.4)
>20 years	1 (0.4)	3 (1.2)	0	3 (1.2)	3 (1.2)

PGY1 = Postgraduate year one; PGY2 = Postgraduate year two.

dispensed topical antibiotic was fusidic acid 5% cream or ointment, reported by 99.6% of participating community pharmacists. Followed by mupirocin cream (53.2%), clindamycin cream (32.6%), silver sulfadiazine 1% cream (20.6%), topical neomycin and bacitracin (13.3%), and the least reported to be dispensed was topical metronidazole (6.4%).

Attitude

Most participating community pharmacists agreed that dispensing topical antibiotics without a prescription was legal in Saudi Arabia (69.1%). In addition, most think that dispensing topical antibiotics without a prescription is a common practice among community pharmacists in Saudi Arabia (77.7%). Regarding the consequences of inappropriate dispensing of topical antibiotics, 82% agreed that it may contribute to antibiotic resistance, and 68.7% agreed that antibiotic resistance in topical antibiotics has become a public health issue. Furthermore, most respondents (78.5%) think dispensing topical antibiotics contributes to patients' inappropriate antibiotic use (Fig. 1). When using univariable logistic regression to explore the association between demographics and attitudes toward antibiotic dispensing, no significant correlation was found except for a positive correlation between agreeing that dispensing topical antibiotics without a prescription is a legal practice in Saudi Arabia and the Eastern Province ($P = 0.023$) and agreeing that dispensing topical antibiotics contributes to the inappropriate use of antibiotics by patients and the PGY1 level of education ($P = 0.005$) (see Suppl. material 1: table S2). It is worth noting that the univariable logistic regression was exploratory, and no multiple adjustments were made.

Knowledge

The participants were asked to match the appropriate indications for ten different topical antibiotics to assess their knowledge. The appropriate indications were based on those approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) (see Suppl. material 1: table S1). Their responses were then divided into three categories: those who identified all correct indications based on the FDA-approved indications, those who identified only some of the FDA-approved indications, and those who did not identify any approved indications (Table 2). The topical antibiotic pharmacists identified all its appropriate indications was clindamycin cream (44.6%). In comparison, more than 50% of pharmacists identified some appropriate indications for benzoyl peroxide gel and neomycin plus bacitracin cream. On the other hand, 90% of the pharmacists could not identify the indications for neomycin 0.1% cream, fusidic acid 5% cream or ointment, and fusidic acid and betamethasone cream.

When safety knowledge was assessed, most pharmacists agreed that the choice of topical antibiotic potency depends on the severity and site of the infection (92.3%) and that some patients can have allergic reactions, such as contact dermatitis, after applying topical antibiotics (78.5%). On the contrary, most disagreed that side effects, such as skin thinning, are common even when topical antibiotics are used appropriately (59.2%) and that topical

antibiotics should not be used to treat affected areas in young children (66.1%).

The majority of participating community pharmacists agreed with all topical antibiotic application statements, including the duration of use (84.5%), the frequency (74.2%), the quantity of application (93.1%), and other items, as summarized in Table 3. Subsequently, most of them agreed with all topical antibiotic formulation statements, such as that the cream formulation is used for large, infected areas (65.2%) and the ointment formulation is used for small, infected areas (70.8%).

Counseling practices and barriers

While 24.4% of the pharmacists reported that they do not specifically counsel patients on the amount of topical antibiotics to apply, most advise applying a thin layer liberally to the affected area (53.2%) and by fingertip units (54.5%). In addition, 33.4% do not have counsel on the expected adverse effects. The most frequently emphasized adverse effects in counseling are superinfection or antibiotic resistance (58.6%) and local skin changes (53.6%). When topical antibiotics are combined with corticosteroids, most pharmacists emphasize immunosuppression (65.2%) when counseling about adverse effects. Participants reported using formal education training (57.9%) and drug reference textbooks and websites (62.6%) as their resources for topical antibiotics counseling. All counseling practices are summarized in Table 4.

One of the biggest obstacles to providing counseling on topical antibiotics is the negative perception that patients often have toward them, as reported by 53.6% of respondents. Other barriers include a lack of time (45%), the assumption that patients are already knowledgeable about topical antibiotics (39%), negative perceptions from doctors about pharmacists' counseling abilities (30.9%), and a lack of available counseling materials (29%).

Discussion

The present study assessed community pharmacists' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding dispensing topical antibiotics in Saudi Arabia. The findings provide valuable insights into the current landscape and highlight important areas for improvement.

Regarding knowledge, our study revealed notable gaps among community pharmacists regarding the appropriate indications for different topical antibiotics. While clindamycin had the highest percentage of pharmacists correctly identifying its indications, significant knowledge gaps remained for other antibiotics. This finding is consistent with previous studies, emphasizing the need for targeted educational interventions to improve pharmacists' knowledge (Amirthalingam et al. 2016). Continuing education programs, workshops, and guideline dissemination should be considered to enhance pharmacists' understanding of appropriate antibiotic use.

Figure 1. Pharmacists' attitude toward topical antibiotics dispensing.

Table 2. Appropriateness of topical antibiotics dispensing for the most common skin diagnosis.

Topical Antibiotic	P1: Pharmacists who identified some of the appropriate indications, N (%)	p-value (P1 vs. P2)	P2: Pharmacists who identified all the appropriate indications, N (%)	p-value (P2 vs. P3)	P3: Pharmacists who did not identify the appropriate indications, N (%)	p-value (P1 vs. P3)
Metronidazole 0.75% cream	82 (35.1)	0.168	4 (1.7)	0.013	147 (63)	<0.001
Clindamycin cream	0	1.000	104 (44.6)	0.103	129 (55.4)	1.000
Silver Sulfadiazine 1% cream	0	1.000	60 (25.8)	<0.001	173 (74.2)	1.000
Neomycin 0.1% cream	9 (3.8)	1.000	0	1.000	224 (96.2)	<0.001
Mupirocin cream	69 (29.6)	0.156	6 (2.5)	<0.001	158 (67.8)	<0.001
Fusidic acid and betamethasone cream	0	1.000	22 (9.4)	<0.001	211 (90.6)	1.000
Topical Benzoyl peroxide gel	172 (73.8)	<0.001	5 (2.1)	0.258	56 (24)	<0.001
Fusidic acid 5% cream or ointment	115 (49.3)	0.332	1 (0.4)	0.322	117 (50.3)	0.896
Fusidic acid and hydrocortisone cream	0	1.000	44 (18.8)	<0.001	189 (81.2)	1.000
Neomycin and bacitracin cream	128 (54.9)	1.000	0	1.000	105 (45.1)	0.134

Table 3. Topical antibiotics safety, application, and formulation knowledge.

Statement	Yes, N (%)	No, N (%)
Safety		
The choice of topical antibiotics potency depends on the severity and site of the infection	215 (92.3)	18 (7.7)
Side effects, such as skin thinning, are common even when topical antibiotics are used appropriately	95 (40.8)	138 (59.2)
Some patients can have allergic reaction such as contact dermatitis after the application of topical antibiotics.	183 (78.5)	50 (21.5)
Topical antibiotics should not be used to treat affected areas in young children.	79 (33.9)	154 (66.1)
Application		
In general, topical antibiotics should be used for 7–14 consecutive days.	197 (84.5)	36 (15.5)
Topical antibiotics should always be applied exactly twice a day.	173 (74.2)	60 (25.8)
A sufficient quantity of topical antibiotics should be applied to cover all affected areas.	217 (93.1)	16 (6.9)
The quantity needed for each application can be measured using the finger-tip unit.	204 (87.6)	29 (12.4)
Topical antibiotics can be used for long term in some cases.	175 (75.1)	58 (24.9)
If a topical antibiotic is needed long term, a regular break in treatment should be incorporated.	176 (75.5)	57 (24.5)
Formulation		
The cream formulation for the topical antibiotics is typically used for large-infected areas.	152 (65.2)	81 (34.8)
The ointment formulation for the topical antibiotics is typically used for small-infected areas.	165 (70.8)	68 (29.2)
The combination of an antibiotic and a corticosteroid is used to treat conditions where the skin is inflamed (eczema or dermatitis) and also infected by bacteria.	209 (89.7)	24 (10.3)

Table 4. Pharmacist self-reported counseling practices in relation to topical antibiotics.

Counseling Item	N	%
The amount of topical antibiotics you instruct patients to apply		
Do not specifically counsel on the amount to apply	57	24.4
Thin layer of medication liberally to the affected area	124	53.2
By No. of grams or ounces used	32	13.7
By how long a container should last	29	12.4
By fingertip units	127	54.5
Adverse effects emphasized in counseling		
Do not specifically counsel on adverse effects	78	33.4
Superinfection or antibiotic resistance	137	58.7
Local skin changes (e.g., skin atrophy or contact dermatitis)	125	53.6
Adverse effects emphasized in counseling when corticosteroids present		
Adrenal suppression	77	33
Immunosuppression	152	65.2
Ocular effects (posterior subcapsular cataracts and glaucoma)	79	33.9
Systemic effects	83	35.6
Others:		
Skin thinning	2	0.85
Resources that inform your topical antibiotics counseling		
Previous patient care experience	87	37.3
Formal educational training	135	57.9
Drug reference textbooks/websites	146	62.6
Medication package inserts	102	43.7
Current research	82	35

Our study identified positive attitudes among pharmacists regarding the consequences of inappropriate dispensing and the contribution of topical antibiotics to antibiotic resistance. This aligns with the growing awareness of the global issue of antibiotic resistance and the role of healthcare professionals in mitigating it. However, we also observed discrepancies between pharmacists' attitudes and reported practices. Despite recognizing the potential harms, many pharmacists reported dispensing topical antibiotics without a prescription. This finding is consistent with previous studies, highlighting a disconnect between awareness and actual behavior (Al-Azzam et al. 2007; Hadi et al. 2016). Another study found that pharmacists with postgraduate qualifications were more likely to hold positive perceptions of and engage in antibiotic stewardship than their non-postgraduate counterparts (Khan et al. 2016). Bridging this gap is crucial to ensure evidence-based practices and should be a key focus of interventions to promote appropriate antibiotic use in community pharmacy settings.

The findings of this study highlight a critical misalignment between pharmacists' professional awareness and their actual dispensing behaviors in Saudi Arabia. While a significant majority (82%) recognized that the inappropriate use of topical antibiotics accelerates antimicrobial resistance, nearly 70% of participants mistakenly believed that dispensing these medications without a prescription remains legal. This confusion likely stems from inconsistent adherence to the Ministry of Health's 2018 regulations, which explicitly prohibit such sales. To address this, a multi-faceted approach is required. Policy

measures should focus on stricter regulatory enforcement, frequent government inspections, and the integration of mandatory digital prescription-monitoring systems to track dispensing in real time. Simultaneously, educational measures must be prioritized, including mandatory Continuous Professional Development (CPD) programs and the dissemination of standardized clinical guidelines to address specific knowledge gaps regarding antibiotic indications and safety. By combining robust policy enforcement with targeted training, healthcare authorities can better empower community pharmacists to serve as effective stewards of antimicrobial use, ultimately safeguarding public health against the rising threat of resistance.

Research across Tanzania, Nepal, Jordan, and Egypt has consistently found high rates of antibiotic dispensing without prescriptions in community pharmacies (Ansari 2017; Horumpende et al. 2018; Abdelaziz et al. 2019; Haddadin et al. 2019). In one of those studies, non-pharmacists often carried out this practice (Ansari 2017). In Saudi Arabia, antibiotics (oral or topical) require a prescription to be dispensed at the community pharmacies. However, there may be some deviation from this regulation. A previous study of ours showed that 5.4% of dispensed antibiotics were purchased from a pharmacy without a prescription (Kurdi et al. 2020). This practice can be associated with issues such as incomplete antibiotic courses, insufficient advice on antibiotic use, and inappropriate antibiotic dispensing. These findings highlight the urgent need for interventions to improve antibiotic dispensing practices in community pharmacies, including enforcing regulations, educating pharmacy staff, and running awareness campaigns. It is

worth noting that the legality of dispensing topical antibiotics without a prescription varies by country, and that there is no apparent evidence of antimicrobial resistance in countries where it can be dispensed without a prescription. Also, some developed countries, such as Canada and the United Kingdom, allow pharmacists to dispense oral antibiotics for urinary tract infections without a prescription. This will likely become a common practice, making it challenging to determine whether dispensing antibiotics without a prescription is appropriate or not without clear guidelines that account for local context.

Furthermore, our study explored counseling practices and identified several barriers community pharmacists face. Time constraints, low patient demand, and inadequate communication between pharmacists and physicians were reported as barriers to counseling. Previous studies identified inadequate knowledge and confidence, lack of time, and poor patient response as key barriers to patient counseling in community pharmacies (Adepu and Nagavi 2009; Albekairy 2014). Another study highlighted the absence of children during medication pickup and a lack of child-friendly materials as specific challenges in engaging pediatric patients (Abraham et al. 2017). Furthermore, Boeni et al. (2015) found that while half of the patients received counseling, only 6.7% included adherence counseling, with barriers including patient rejection and lack of time. These studies underscore the need for improved pharmacist training, better patient engagement strategies, and the development of child-friendly materials to enhance patient counseling in community pharmacies.

Historically, more non-Saudis than Saudis have worked in community pharmacies, since most Saudis have targeted hospitals and clinical fields. While this has changed recently with more Saudi pharmacy graduates entering community pharmacies and industries, the balance has yet to be achieved. However, this will not affect the reported data, as all pharmacists (Saudis or not) must meet the same qualifications and pass the same licensing exams before working in community pharmacies. Furthermore, they must all follow the same legal practices in the country. Nevertheless, our study suggests that some of them still do not comply with the country's legislation on dispensing antibiotics without a prescription.

Our study has certain limitations that need to be acknowledged. First, the sample size was smaller than we had initially intended, and the response rate was approximately 5.8%. This may limit the generalizability of our findings to the entire population of community pharmacists in Saudi Arabia and raise concerns about potential nonresponse bias. In other words, those who responded may have differed from those who did not, which could have influenced our results. Therefore, we need to conduct future studies with larger sample sizes and higher response rates to validate and expand upon our findings. However, it is worth mentioning that a community pharmacy in Saudi Arabia is typically run by a single pharmacist. With 233 participants in our study, the sample will represent 233 pharmacies. Second, our study relied on self-reported

data, which may have introduced social desirability bias. In other words, participants may have provided answers that were more socially acceptable rather than being completely honest. We must use objective measures such as direct observation of pharmacists' practices or chart reviews to obtain a more accurate and reliable understanding of dispensing behaviors. This will provide more robust insights into community pharmacists' actual practices in Saudi Arabia. Third, some statements that asked about topical antibiotic safety, application, and formulation knowledge that should be answered with a single yes or no actually might contain two statements, which makes the interpretation of the results challenging (e.g., the statement "The choice of topical antibiotics potency depends on the severity and site of the infection" is asking about two parameters in one question). Fourth, it would be more insightful to present the distribution of dispenses relative to the total number of customers at the pharmacy. However, we could not access this type of data using the study's cross-sectional design. We collected the number of topical antibiotic prescriptions directly from pharmacists. Fifth, fewer participants had PGY1 or PGY2 degrees, which was reflected in the wide CIs and large estimates when examining the association between demographics and attitudes toward antibiotic dispensing. Finally, dispensing antibiotics is not the same as using them. Inappropriate dispensing eventually leads to antibiotic overuse. However, our study did not aim to measure antibiotic use, as it sought to explore the community pharmacy perspective on this matter.

To enhance patient education and promote the rational use of antibiotics in community pharmacy settings, further research is needed that focuses on various aspects. Firstly, interventions in this regard should be evaluated to assess their effectiveness in achieving the desired outcomes. Secondly, objective measures of practices should be incorporated to ensure that the interventions are being implemented as intended. These measures can include monitoring dispensing patterns, assessing the appropriateness of antibiotic prescriptions, and measuring patient outcomes. Finally, exploring additional strategies to optimize antibiotic dispensing can provide further insights into promoting the rational use of antibiotics in community pharmacies. Such strategies can include pharmacist-led patient education and counseling programs, implementation of clinical decision support tools, and collaborative efforts with healthcare providers to promote appropriate antibiotic use. By taking a comprehensive approach to addressing this issue, we can ensure that antibiotics are used appropriately and effectively to improve patient outcomes and reduce the risk of antibiotic resistance.

Conclusions

This cross-sectional study highlights community pharmacists' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding the dispensing of topical antibiotics in Saudi Arabia. The findings reveal several gaps in understanding and adherence

to guidelines among pharmacists, including variations in knowledge of appropriate indications and gaps in addressing expected adverse effects during counseling. It is evident that targeted interventions are necessary to enhance pharmacists' understanding of regulations, improve knowledge of appropriate antibiotic use, and overcome barriers to effective counseling. Strengthening education and training programs, providing comprehensive guidelines, and promoting responsible antibiotic use in community pharmacies are crucial to enhancing patient safety and optimizing healthcare outcomes. By addressing these issues, healthcare providers and policymakers can work together to improve the quality and safety of pharmacy services and promote responsible antibiotic use in the community, ultimately combating the global challenge of antibiotic resistance.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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Use of AI

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, H.W.; methodology, H.W., and S.K.; validation, H.W.; formal analysis, S.K.; investigation, H.W., and S.K.; data curation, S.K.; writing – original draft preparation, H.W. and S.K.; writing – review and editing, H.W. and S.K.; visualization, H.W. and S.K.; project administration, H.W.; funding acquisition, S.K. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

The data underpinning the analysis reported in this paper are deposited at Kurdi, Sawsan; Wali, Haytham (2026), "Dispensing and Counseling Practices of Topical Antibiotics Among Community Pharmacists in Saudi Arabia: A Cross-sectional Study", Mendeley Data, V1, <https://doi.org/10.17632/vcvfx3k94m.1>.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary data

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Data type: docx

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